

Growth Strategies of Mobile Commerce In India

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Chandrasekaran, S & Narayanan, M. "Growth Strategies of Mobile Commerce in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 111–115.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552228>

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Abstract

M-Commerce is an emerging discipline involving applications, mobile device, middleware, and wireless networks. While most of existing E-Commerce application can be modified to run a wireless environment, M-Commerce also involves many more new applications that become possible only due to the wireless infrastructure. The future Mobile commerce is the next logical step for Indian merchants. With the growth of mobile phones and increased issuing and use of debit and credit cards, mobile commerce will deliver strong growth over the coming years. Mobile technology gives us the edge over our competitors.

Keywords: mobile commerce, mobile commerce applications and discussion of m – commerce application users benefits and satisfaction, etc.,

Introduction

M-commerce has never been separated from e-commerce. M-commerce has always been considered as part of the e-commerce industry. It is time to discuss the same separately. E-commerce has witnessed phenomenal growth in India in the last five years and is expected to grow from USD 39 billion revenue in 2017 to USD 120 billion by 2020, CAGR of over 50% according to a report by IBEF. Now, is the turn of m-Commerce. What has contributed to the growth of e-commerce is the penetration of internet. Today, there are 480 million plus internet users with 80% of them in urban India and 20% in rural India.

Mobile phone is a clear proof of the advances in telecommunication that led to the development of most countries. Today, most people, even children, all around the world carry their mobile phones wherever they go. Therefore, mobile phone designers try to exploit this device as much as they can. Earlier, people used mobile phones just to receive calls and send text messages. However, with each passing day, designers have succeeded in attracting more users by continually improving this device. Nowadays, mobile phones are not just used for receiving phone calls or sending text messages, but are used to provide more service with different features to its users.

These services are part of mobile commerce (M-commerce).

Objectives of the Study

- To analyse the usage of mobile commerce service and its applications.
- To find out the problems facing by consumer in mobile commerce activities.
- To know the level of benefits enjoying consumer on mobile commerce.

Review of Literature

Dr. D. Sriram, Associate Professor, Marketing, Great Lakes Institute of Management, Chennai, mobile apps will only continue to improve, expand and redefine customer experience. “Customized mobile apps, increased multi-media content, mobile image recognition and near-field communication technologies will help organizations to fine tune, customize and deliver a unique experience to customers,” he opined.

Christian Chadwick, Director, Whipped. in, a unit of SWS hospitality Pvt. Ltd feels by opening up your business to m-commerce, you’re massively increasing your customer base and also the frequency in which a customer might order from you. “With the meteoric rise of the payment wallet, such as Paytm or Mobikwik, customers are encouraged with the offer of big discounts, to order through and pay for products through their mobile device.

Research Methodology

The nature of the research on m-commerce, it would be difficult to group the literature under any specific disciplines. Further evidence of this can be seen from the fact that m-commerce articles are scattered across various journals in disciplines such as business, management, marketing, engineering, information technology (IT), and information systems (IS). Consequently, various online journal databases. Were selected and searched to provide a comprehensive bibliography on m-commerce literature. The literature search was based on the descriptor, mobile commerce or m-commerce. The search was also limited to peer reviewed journal articles.

Mobile Commerce

Mobile Commerce, also called m-commerce or m-commerce, includes any monetary transaction completed using a mobile device. It is an advancement of ecommerce, enabling people to buy and sell goods or services from almost anywhere, simply using a mobile phone or tablet device.

M-Commerce Services

M-Commerce is an emerging discipline involving applications, mobile device, middleware, and wireless networks. While most of existing E-Commerce application can be modified to run a wireless environment, M-Commerce also involves many more new applications that become possible only due to the wireless infrastructure. These applications include mobile financial services, user and location specific mobile advertising, mobile inventory management, wireless business re-engineering, and mobile interactive games. In addition to device and wireless constraints, M-commerce would also be impacted by the dependability of wireless infrastructure. M-Commerce existing and futures possible application include:

M-Commerce Services and Applications

Mobile Banking	Mobile Accounting, Mobile Brokerage, Mobile Financial Information
Mobile Entertainment	Mobile Gaming, Download of Music and Ring tones , Download of Video and Digital Images, Location-Based entertainment services
Mobile Information Services	Current affairs(financial ,sport and other news) Travel information, Tracking services(persons and Objects), Mobile search engines
Mobile Marketing	Mobile Couponing Direct(Context-Sensitive) Marketing• Organization of Mobile Events• Mobile newsletters•
Mobile Shopping	Mobile purchasing of goods and services
Mobile Ticketing	Public Transport Sports and cultural Events• Air and rail Traffic• Mobile Parking•
Telematics Services	Remote diagnosis and maintenance of vehicles Navigation services• Vehicle tracking and theft protection• Emergency Services•

Discussion of M- Commerce application usage in India

Relationship between gender and level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone
t- test

Factors	Gender						T value		
	Male			Female			P value		
	Banking Apps	60	4.4833	.79173	40	3.6000	1.39229	.000	3.639
Social and Gaming Apps	60	3.8000	1.19036	40	4.2500	.89872	.099	2.034	.045
Retail store Apps	60	3.4500	1.1992	40	3.6250	1.352822	.337	.679	.499
Ticketing	60	3.1833	1.53737	40	3.3000	1.28502	.054	.399	.691
Information Services	60	3.0833	1.30568	40	3.5250	1.24009	.687	1.690	.094

Since p value is .000 less than 0.05, then null hypothesis is rejected at 5 % significance level. Hence there is significant relationship between male and female in respect to level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone.

Since p value is .099 more than 0.05, then null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % significance level. Hence there is no significant relationship between male and female in respect to level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone.

Since p value is .337 more than 0.05, then null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % significance level. Hence there is no significant relationship between male and female in respect to level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone.

Since p value is .054 more than 0.05, then null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % significance level. Hence there is no significant relationship between male and female in respect to level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone.

Since p value is .687 more than 0.05, then null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % significance level. Hence there is no significant relationship between male and female in respect to level of usage of different mobile apps in mobile phone.

Level of Benefits of using Mobile Commerce

Weighted Average

S.No	Benefits	Frequency					Weighted score	Rank
		Very high	High	Average	Low	Very		
1.	Cost Saving	125	176	48	18	6	3.73	3
2.	Time Saving	220	132	39	8	6	4.05	1
3.	24 hrs access	175	136	57	18	3	3.89	2
4.	Physical Security	110	64	138	30	1	3.43	4
5.	Others	70	44	99	48	18	2.79	5

That time saving has been given the first place by the respondents for the benefits they have obtained with the average score of 4.05 which is followed by 24 hours access with the weighted score of 3.89 has been given the second place, cost saving with weighted score of 3.73 has been given the third place, physical security with weighted score of 3.43 has been given the fourth place and the least weighted score has been given to other benefits.

Therefore it is concluded that the majority of the respondents has obtained the benefit of time saving.

Suggestions

- Offering more facilities and benefits to the mobile users so that all age group of respondents will use their mobile phone for their shopping purpose.
- Encourage the government employee in terms of offering training facility, disseminating the government policies and regulations through social network. So that they will be induced to use the mobile phone for their professional and commercial purposes.
- Offer special discounts and use sales improvement techniques through mobile phone so that people will get interest to use mobile phone for their shopping.
- We strongly suggest that the nationalized bank to offer credit facility to the youth with lower rate of interest. So that they will be tempted to use mobile phone for credit purchase.
- Pay attention on prompt delivery, bear the loss for delivering damaged products, cash on delivery system. They will make the customer to get strongly agree from mobile shopping experience.

Conclusion

Mobile commerce play important role infecting human life. Mobile Commerce’s future seems to be extremely safe. In the previous few years it has been seen that the potential of M-commerce has paved a way to new emerging practices for businesses in today’s world and India is also showing the positive prints of adaptation of M-commerce platform for the same. The increasing demand of M-commerce applications in India shows that it has penetrated the Indian market but still M-commerce is at nascent stage in India and is evolving every passing day. And some barriers like lack of user trust and awareness in M-commerce and m-commerce technology, usability problems & language barriers, low internet connectivity, technical limitations and doubts about security and lack of widely accepted standards can little hinder the growth of m-commerce in India.

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